

INFRAEDI-02-2018

www.bioexcel.eu

BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D1.5– Long-term hardware and application roadmap

WP1: Code optimization & scaling

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Document Information

Deliverable Number	D1.5
Deliverable Name	Long-term hardware and application roadmap
Due Date	2021-10-31 (PM34)
Deliverable Lead	KTH
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Keywords	Software development
WP	WP1
Nature	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Final Version Date	2021-10-27
Reviewed by	Rosa Badia (BSC) Stian Soiland-Reyes (UNIMAN)
MGT Board Approval	2021-10-28

Document History

Partner	Date	Comments	Version
KTH	2021-09-14	First draft	0.1
KTH	2021-09-20	GROMACS roadmap updated	0.2
MPG	2021-09-23	PMX roadmap updated	0.3
UEDIN/JYU /UU	2021-09-30	CP2K and HADDOCK roadmaps updated	0.4
JYU/UEDIN /MPG/UU/ KTH	2021-10-05	Minor corrections on all content	0.5
UNIMAN/JY U/MPG/KT H	2021-10-20	Final version	0.6

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports updates on the BioExcel-2 core application roadmaps as presented in deliverable D1.3. The roadmaps have been updated for work performed, as well as for changes in needs driven by both developments on the hardware side and requests of users. In addition, there have been changes in prioritization and new tasks added due to the outbreak of Covid-19, which has spurred a massive amount of research in life sciences. This, in combination with the no-cost extension of the BioExcel-2 project duration, has led to some development tasks being moved to the extension period.

The **GROMACS** development has focused on a number of key user-requested features, in particular adding multiple time stepping, driving simulations with external data, facilitating generation of input data, and better free energy tools. Some of this is still ongoing and a few new user requests have been identified that are worth implementing. The development of performance optimization has prioritized porting of the GPU acceleration of GROMACS to SYCL, targeting AMD GPUs for the new LUMI pre-exascale machine. Also multi-GPU PME is nearly ready through co-design with NVIDIA. Focus on these urgent tasks has meant work on other tasks started later. For the medium term, future effort is planned on performant and flexible APIs to enable more flexible ensemble parallelism for the Exascale.

The development of the **PMX** package followed two main directions. Firstly, the core code was updated with the changes necessary for the successful future usability of the software. In particular, considering the depreciation of Python2, pmx was rewritten in Python3. The continuous support of the main pmx functionalities was ensured. The second major development direction comprises the incorporation of features frequently requested by users, the addition of new mutation libraries and creation of workflows for free energy calculation setup and analysis.

HADDOCK's development focuses on the continuous improvement of the web server, which functions as the main user's interface, the implementation of relevant features and the design of the new version HADDOCK3. The web server is being co-developed alongside the local HADDOCK version, so that new features (coarse-grained and shape docking, etc.) are readily available in an intuitive and responsive user-friendly interface. A major rework of the current code is in place for what will become HADDOCK3, with a modular design we aim to provide flexibility for workflow creation and a straightforward framework to integrate new tools. This new modular architecture will also enable more efficient execution on HPC resources.

To provide users with access to chemical reactivity in biomolecular simulations, we will develop an interface between GROMACS and CP2K, a highly parallelized density functional theory (DFT) computer program. With the new interface, users can perform multi-scale simulations, in which one part of the system is modelled with DFT, while the remainder is described with a molecular mechanics force field (i.e. QM/MM). Our developments focus on providing the community with an

accurate, scalable and user-friendly QM/MM solution. Compared to the previous BioExcel software roadmap, which focused on CPMD for DFT functionality in QM/MM simulations, this updated roadmap reflects the project's transition to CP2K, which has more wide-spread availability and uptake in the community.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents updates of roadmaps presented in BioExcel deliverable “D1.3 Updated software roadmaps” in December 2019 (pending approval).

One of the most important impact items for BioExcel-2 is that the Centre-of-Excellence supports, maintains, and develops some of the most widely used software in the field of computational biomolecular science. These codes are used by thousands of academic and industrial research groups, they have enabled dozens of projects in PRACE, EuroHPC and other international HPC organizations, and many of the codes are highly involved in co-design efforts with industry to design next-generation hardware as well as software that is better at addressing concrete scientific and industrial challenges.

BioExcel-2 (as BioExcel) is a highly user-driven CoE: Investments in software and support are prioritized based on the impact the work will have for users. This has been based on questionnaires, user feedback at BioExcel workshops and forums, as well as in-depth interviews with selected users and industry site visits. Many of the features currently on the code roadmaps have originated this way, but there are also critically important challenges to the entire field that might not be immediately obvious to individual users, such as e.g.:

- making sure codes will run efficiently on future (ideally European) hardware yet to be announced,
- implementing acceleration for multi-GPU systems which are common in the pre-Exascale EuroHPC installations,
- developing solutions to make it possible for communities previously not using large-scale HPC to move to this type of resources, e.g. through better handling of massive I/O, throughput-focused computing, and big data,
- achieving scaling on systems with order-of-magnitude more processors than what is available today to target the Exascale systems, for instance by moving to ensemble techniques for small systems,
- achieving interoperability between all major codes in the field to enable completely new types of workflows, while also prioritizing mutual interoperability between leading European HPC codes,
- developing stable and performant APIs is important for the previous point as well as for maintainability of codes, as it improves modularity and clarifies responsibilities,
- leading rather than merely participating in the international community, e.g. by ensuring *all* common codes produce similar results, and helping users (as well as the community) to make better choices,
- sharing knowledge such that advances by BioExcel can also be implemented in other codes,

Challenges like these have been prioritized based on input e.g. from the PRACE SSC Scientific Case, the user needs, benchmarks and hosting reports from EuroHPC, roadmaps from the European Processor Initiative, several international organizations and interviews with key opinion leaders. BioExcel and BioExcel-2 have also established strategic collaboration with the US-based MoISSI center, we have organized and participated in a number of joint workshops to promote code interoperability, and in addition the BioExcel Scientific Director sits on several

scientific advisory boards of centers maintaining other key codes such as NAMD and VMD, which has led to a number of close collaborations and aligned strategic plans that have the potential to fundamentally transform how researchers use all the codes in the field, not only the ones maintained within BioExcel.

2 General requirements of biomolecular software

Scientific computing in general, and life science in particular, have large requirements not only for scaling, performance and features, but even more for quality assurance, extensive testing, ability to compare algorithms and results, having access to the code to critically assess an implementation, and strong provenance of results such as tracking exact source code versions and compilers used to be able to identify bugs or deviations.

In addition, users increasingly need to combine a number of different tools in workflows (adding demands for data interoperability), while using very flexible ways of generating input data through interactive options such as graphical interfaces or websites.

Encouraged by users, developer communities are working towards common terminologies and specifications across codes, to improve portability of results and settings.

Growing in importance for a variety of users is support for new hardware with emerging accelerator platforms, in particular to handle data growing in throughput, size and frequency of processing. An ongoing challenge, particular for industry users, is the desire to combine dedicated private compute infrastructure with on-demand scaling to cloud resources, which implies supporting a more heterogeneous and diverse set of hardware, operating systems and data management strategies.

Of increasing importance is flexible *installation options*. A system administrator might prefer standard Linux packages, while other sites need to customize installations. As an example, users in industry or strongly controlled environments have expressed needs for downloading a plain binary that can be run from a home directory without having to request an administrator to add or update a package across their company-wide IT infrastructure.

While BioExcel itself cannot solve all of these needs, they have been critical components in the development and prioritization of all software roadmaps in the CoE.

3 Long-term development plans for GROMACS

For GROMACS, a large number of important directions for future development have been identified. These are listed here but are not ordered into a formal timeline.

In practice, requirements from other funding resources will shift over time, and rarely can any developer focus solely on one task in order to deliver it by a predictable date, given that a feature often depends on several other features and that the development team also spends an increasing part of their time on quality assurance (QA) of previously completed features.

The skill set of available developers often determines which targets can receive most effort. Progress is also contingent upon the availability of resources for testing, and since GROMACS has moved to a full formal code review process, this also requires time and availability for the review of the code by other expert developers.

It should be noted that GROMACS does not only target bio-molecular simulations, and the software is increasingly being used in other areas. For the first time, several of the planned targets reflect the needs of other domains like materials science and flow simulations.

Finally, as part of BioExcel and the mission of supporting broader types of simulations for the community, the GROMACS project has been collaborating much closer (in particular for training) with Amber & NAMD, which are the other two major codes in the field, and these new collaborations are likely to influence future development of all of these codes.

Several items planned on the previous roadmaps have now been partially or fully implemented, with features such as enhanced sampling techniques (the Accelerated Weight Histogram method (AWH)) available in GROMACS 2018, recently extended to alchemical calculations in GROMACS 2021, as well as the initial support for the Python API in GROMACS 2019. Additionally, we have extended NVIDIA support to now support complete GROMACS simulations running on GPUs and have expanded the ability to use experimental data to drive simulations, which was added in the GROMACS 2021 release.

Over the past years we have made major advances in performance, features and code organization and quality. There have also been improvements in usability, especially for new functionality, but this will be a stronger focus in the current plans.

For performance, more parts of the computation have been ported to be able to execute on GPUs. GROMACS has also been ported to the newest SIMD architectures, including ARM_SVE in GROMACS 2021. The inclusion of the *accelerated weight histogram* method enables accelerated sampling with a simple user interface and this method has already proven to be popular with users. This has recently been extended to alchemical free-energy calculations.

Many error messages have been clarified and more checks on user input have been added. The GROMACS test coverage has been expanded to improve reliability. To enable all this, a significant amount of refactoring and rewriting of legacy code has taken place. Although this has taken quite some time, it pays off in maintainability and provides better extensibility over the next years.

There have been several significant performance improvements in existing algorithms, in particular for free-energy calculations. Most algorithms in GROMACS had been ported to GPUs, but not in combination with free-energy calculations. Now all parts of free-energy calculations, except for the non-bonded pair interactions, can be run on GPUs. The performance on the non-bonded pair interactions on the CPU has also been improved.

Through the development of current experimental methods, more and more different methods are available to investigate protein structures and dynamics. As a result of work in BioExcel and BioExcel-2 GROMACS now supports using experimental Cryo-EM density maps to bias MD simulations.

The code review, continuous integration and issue tracking of GROMACS has been moved from three separate systems to the integrated GitLab platform <https://gitlab.com/GROMACS>. This has streamlined the development process and has significantly lowered the maintenance burden of the testing framework. Being similar to GitHub, this collaboration method is commonly recognized, so it is easier for new developers to participate.

Feedback from users has led to prioritization of certain issues and features. One example is the performance of free-energy calculations. Users regularly complained about this at BioExcel workshops. Also, pharmaceutical companies have indicated that this is a weak point of GROMACS compared to other codes. A second example is the request for more flexible reaction coordination definitions, which would enable users to easily and efficiently sample functional transitions in biomolecules.

3.1 Evolution of Exascale-suitable task parallelism

In particular when combined with domain decomposition between computational nodes, the rapidly increasing core counts is making it difficult to parallelize all tasks over all cores due to the limited size of data on each node. To address this, GROMACS developers plan to reformulate the entire molecular dynamics simulation algorithm into fine-grained task graphs where each task only runs on a subset of cores, communication is also formulated as tasks, and dynamic data dependencies are tracked to avoid global barriers. Presently there are few if any task libraries that support the type of extremely low-latency tasks needed for such an approach. Therefore, we are both evaluating the new OpenMP 5.0 task features while also working with two hardware vendors on co-design projects that involve future task libraries.

3.2 Deployment and acceleration for new EuroHPC architectures

We are continuously improving the GROMACS SIMD acceleration layer to target all major platforms and have recently started a new co-design project focused on the ARM Scalable Vector Extensions (SVE). The code also takes advantage of GPU accelerators and now supports the calculation of close to all interaction types on those devices for CUDA-based platforms, and non-bonded short-range interactions and PME long-range interactions on devices that support OpenCL.

GROMACS has support for non-Nvidia GPUs through the OpenCL platform. However, this open standard has lost momentum and instead the new SYCL platform is being adopted by hardware vendors such as Intel and AMD. Because the new pre-exascale system LUMI will soon have its AMD GPU partition online, adding support for SYCL has become rather urgent. Build system support and non-bonded compute kernels for SYCL are expected to be part of the GROMACS 2022 release. But as SYCL uses a completely different approach to asynchronous task scheduling than CUDA, a large amount of effort is needed to port all algorithms currently supported by CUDA in GROMACS to SYCL. As SYCL is an open and modern standard, there is hope that nearly all future architectures will support this, so that the GROMACS GPU algorithms do not need to be ported to a fourth platform after adapting SYCL.

For 2021, GROMACS is focussing on extended OpenCL support to both AMD and Intel platforms, improved multi-GPU scaling for CUDA, and beyond this we have new co-design projects targeting native acceleration for both CUDA, SYCL and HIP that covers all current major accelerator vendors (NVIDIA, AMD, Intel). We are monitoring EuroHPC developments, if they select a different API for a potential European accelerator, we would also be highly interested in implementing support for this hardware assuming development resources are available.

3.3 Extend Accelerator/GPU-only simulation support

During BioExcel-2 we have worked on enabling steps between pair search and domain decomposition partitioning to run nearly fully on the GPU. Only the temperature and pressure calculation and the thermo- and barostat integration run on CPU, but these typically occur only every 10 steps. This removes the bottleneck where high-end GPUs presently must be paired with an expensive CPU and it also removes the bottleneck of PCI transfer overheads, particularly on high-end systems. Currently most of this functionality is limited to CUDA GPUs.

We would like to extend this to all major accelerator platforms, but that will likely require additional development resources. Also the remaining common operations should be ported to the GPU, both for performance and to simplify the run schedule. This will provide a setup where special algorithms, such as density-driven fitting or other methods whose forces can be applied with multiple time stepping, need to be written only once for the CPU, which minimizes developer time, while still having close to optimal total run performance.

3.4 Parallel version of PME on GPUs

The particle-mesh Ewald algorithm is what limits scaling of MD simulations. For CPU-only or combined CPU-GPU runs we have a relatively efficient MPI parallel version of both the *atom to grid to atom* spread and gather operations as well as for the 3D FFT. However, as GPUs get faster, there is direct-GPU communication and especially now that there are HPC machines (e.g. LUMI) where the network is directly coupled to the GPU instead of the CPU, there are large benefits to running PME on multiple GPUs. To achieve this, we first move the spread and gather compute kernels to the GPU, together with the grid overlap communication, combined with FFTs on the CPU. As better parallel 3D-FFT GPUs become available, we will interface with those to achieve maximum performance on new (pre-) exascale machines such as LUMI.

3.5 Automated performance optimization

With ever more components of GROMACS being supported for GPU offloading, it can become challenging for end-users to configure a given simulation system for optimal performance on their particular hardware. There are simply too many combinations of options to try, and while BioExcel have developed short-run benchmarks, they may not always give a realistic picture as performance characteristics depend also on individual simulation data and settings.

This challenge should be addressed by a combination of pre-computed cross-over points and auto-tuning during simulation by dynamically moving computation between CPU and GPU depending on load and actual performance. This will help unlock the full GROMACS performance for every user.

3.6 Investigate performance improvements through multiple time stepping

Currently GROMACS supports doubling of the time-step, and a near doubling of the performance, by replacing hydrogen atoms by *virtual interactions sites*. The disadvantages of this approach are that the topology is (automatically) modified, extra particles appear in the output and it is not supported for general small (drug) molecules. In GROMACS 2021 a, flexible, multiple time stepping method was implemented. This enables near doubling of the performance by doubling the time step at which most forces are computed. Most importantly, this is transparent to the user. However, with full doubling of the time step, some hydrogen atoms in two popular force fields have a very small, but not negligible, probability of becoming unstable. We need to find the best setup of multiple stepping which provides a significant performance gain without such instabilities.

3.7 Support for fast multipole electrostatics for better scaling

GROMACS, like most molecular simulation packages, use the *particle-mesh Ewald* (PME) algorithm to compute long-range electrostatics interactions. PME achieves

high serial performance through the use of *fast Fourier transforms* (FFTs), but these strongly limit parallel scaling due to the higher number of communications required.

A hierarchical method such as the *fast-multipole method* (FMM) has much lower communication needs and therefore provides better scaling, which becomes critical when scaling large systems to millions of cores. A fundamental issue with FMM has been that it does not conserve energy, which is a requirement for molecular dynamics. Recently we have developed and demonstrated improvements to FMM to obtain energy conservation. This paves the way for the application of FMM to molecular dynamics. We are working with two leading groups in Europe and Japan to incorporate their FMM codes in GROMACS.

3.8 Support for tabulated interactions for CPU and GPU architectures

Many knowledge-based force fields, particularly in materials science, produce interaction functions that are not based on an easily described mathematical formula. The potential and force for such interactions must be looked up from tables for each particle pair. The use of such kernels needs care because one must choose interpolation schemes that are able to run fast on the hardware, while providing a bounded error range.

To make use of such tabulated interactions, the topology description within GROMACS must be extended so that it is possible to choose tables for unique atom pairs, or pairs of all types, etc. This would significantly enhance the usability of GROMACS for non-traditional applications, including both materials science and special potentials currently only available on slow or non-scaling simulation codes.

3.9 Support for polarizable force fields

Most biomolecular simulations and calculations are performed with force fields with fixed partial charges. Although this works quite well, this is an approximation as it ignores atomic polarizability. Atomic polarizability can have a large effect on interactions when molecules or groups of atoms change the environment, like during the binding of a drug molecule.

GROMACS has long supported the so-called *shell model* for atomic polarizability. But with the expanding efforts on polarizable force fields over the last decade, supporting other polarization models is possible. Collaborators are working on an implementation of the polarizable version of the popular CHARMM force field in GROMACS, this work should be integrated. Furthermore, it can be useful, in particular for polarizable models, to describe charges as a distribution instead of point charges. Support for this needs to be added in the pair-interaction kernels.

3.10 Improve free-energy performance

Free-energy calculations are an important class of calculation in GROMACS, both for academia and (pharmaceutical) industry. They are used, for example, during drug development. These are typical throughput calculations and as such suitable for GPU clusters. However, the free-energy pair interaction kernel only runs on the CPU and is an order of magnitude slower than the normal pair kernel. Furthermore, two expensive PME mesh calculations might be needed, which can currently not be offloaded to the GPU. The fact that free-energy calculations are much slower than running the same system without free-energy, particularly on GPUs, has caused this to be the most “popular” performance topic users complain about, both in academia and industry. Therefore it is worth investing effort into optimizing this.

The free-energy PME setup has recently been ported to GPUs and the non-bonded kernel has been optimized by removing calculations with zero pre-factor. But there is still a large gain to be had, as the free-energy kernel is the only compute intensive kernel that does not have a SIMD version. We are also considering porting this to GPUs.

3.11 Simplified free-energy calculations

Although solvation and binding free-energy calculations in GROMACS have been simplified a lot by the decoupling option which avoids editing topologies, setting up the (unphysical) path between the end states is currently still tedious, has too many technical parameters and requires manual optimization. We have, after deprecation warnings, removed esoteric, little used options and are investigate a new, simpler soft-core scheme with more intuitive and less sensitive parameters. More automation will also be added, such that the user does not have to edit numbers in parameters files and manually manage simulations. The user should only have to select a few method options and a scripted procedure takes care of setting up and running all simulations and the postprocessing to obtain the free-energy. In GROMACS 2021 the Accelerated Weight Histogram method has been coupled to the free-energy path. This provides much simpler logistics and more flexible parallelization for free-energy calculations, but more wide-spread application is needed to see if this will become the method of choice. Tighter integration with PMX is planned for the automation.

3.12 More freedom in defining reaction coordinates

A significant part of the simulation studies of bio-molecules is dedicated to understanding functional motions. There are often slow on the MD time scale and involve free-energy barriers. Enhanced sampling techniques can often speed up transitions by several orders of magnitude. But this requires that one can define a sufficiently good reaction coordinate. Currently GROMACS supports distances, angles and dihedrals. Many users have requested “contact” reaction coordinates and linear combinations of multiple coordinates. We plan to enable arbitrary, user-provided mathematical formulas as a reaction coordinate that operate on

one or more base coordinates. This will enable efficient sampling along nearly any possible reaction coordinate.

3.13 Implement performant and stable C++ and Python library APIs

To enable improved access to individual parts of GROMACS functionality, more of the internal parts will be exposed through a stable interface both on the C++ and Python level. The current versions of those features allow users to specify different workflows and dependencies on the Python level, as well as the use of all of the GROMACS tools from Python. As the need for workflows and especially ensemble simulation is increasing, there is a strong need for more flexibility in the APIs. Many workflows and algorithms need to only change coordinates or a few parameters. This would be much more performant, as well as simpler for the user, when this can be done through modification of the variables/parameters the user wants to change and keeping all data in memory rather than regenerating the whole run setup as is currently often required. Having this functionality will allow scripting of more advanced workflows and algorithms instead of needing to code this inside GROMACS. This will significantly lower the barrier for trying new simulation approaches and also improves the maintainability of GROMACS.

In addition, future work will be aimed at stabilizing the exposed API on the C++ level by improving modularization of the code, which is concurrently a requirement for enabling changes in the state and parameters of the system.

3.14 Streamlining of simulation preparation tools

In addition to the core simulation engine and sampling algorithm libraries, GROMACS also packages numerous tools suitable for preparing simulation topologies and conformations. Currently the interfaces to these are complex and some tools are slow. For many, and especially novice users, it would be useful to be able to generate a run setup while only specifying a PDB file, a forcefield and a simulation length. This also simplifies setting up pipelines for studies on many different systems. For standard run setups no further user interaction should be needed, and the system can be automatically solvated in water and neutralized with counter ions. Those changes will remove the need of the users to directly interact with the legacy *pdb2gmx* conversion tool, that has been indicated as one of the major hurdles for users starting new simulations with GROMACS.

3.15 Expansion and modernization of trajectory-analysis tool suite

While work during BioExcel has led to major improvements to the trajectory analysis tool suite and now allows replacing part of the legacy tools for writing modified trajectories and extracting information from them, there is still significant work to be done porting legacy tools to the new framework. Another focus point of future work is the ability to express the requirements of analysis tools regarding the format of the provided trajectory data in a programmatic way. This will ensure that users will no longer have to perform manual conversions

between the results of a simulation and the input for the analysis. The project aims to fully implement those requirements for the existing tools and extending them to all other tools that are being ported to the new analysis suite.

3.16 Constant-pH simulations

Choosing the protonation state for (de)protonatable groups on proteins is problematic, because hydrogen atoms are usually not resolved in X-ray crystallography and the local acid dissociation constant (K_a) values of the ionizable groups, in most cases, are not known. Furthermore, most biomolecular systems show important changes in response to pH, and the local pH for a molecule can change when it moves through the system. Changes in protonation states can have rather large effects due to a local change in electrostatic potential. However, the chemical modification is rather small and can be mimicked by gradually moving the interactions of a proton from one site in the system to another. We have recently developed a very efficient algorithm for simulating dynamics protonation, although it needs to be refactored and fully integrated before releasing it. Dynamic protonation will enable simulating many interesting biological processes and also makes the initial choice of protonation states less critical or superfluous.

3.17 Molecular dynamics for large systems

Simulations of large systems pose particular challenges for simulation software. Large systems occur often in flow applications, but are also getting more common in the biomolecular field with simulation of virus capsids and small cells. Large systems cover larger coordinates in space, which means less absolute precision is available. The main effect that deteriorates the quality of the results is larger noise, due to rounding errors in the integration. One remedy is compiling GROMACS in double precision (for small systems single precision has proved sufficient), but that affects performance significantly and excludes the use of general purpose GPUs (even GPUs that support double precision do so with a significant performance hit). A more elegant solution is storing the coordinates in fixed precision using 32-bit integers. This results in a factor 100 lower rounding errors at little extra cost. Due to the fixed precision, the rounding errors are independent of the value of the coordinates.

3.18 Flexible input format

Historically, GROMACS defined its own plain text key-value input file, implementing its own parser and requiring users to understand how to use it. This was a good decision when it was made, but now that standard formats and libraries for handling structured text input files exist, we plan to transition using these. The best candidate for the format is currently JSON. This will eliminate many kinds of possible bugs in the code and support the modularization efforts elsewhere. Users will be able to edit the structured files in a syntax-aware editor

of their choice. Developers extending the functionality of GROMACS will be able to make changes only in their new module, and not in multiple parts of the code.

3.19 Support for Markov state model ensemble parallelism

Ensemble algorithms provide another level of parallelism, which is becoming critical to enable efficient usage of large HPC resources even for small systems such as proteins. While this is already supported in many ways in the main code base, the data analysis can often only be done using external tools, as in the case of constructing Markov state models (MSMs). Here, users would benefit from being able to use the GROMACS tools directly to perform some of the tasks needed to construct those MSMs, such as efficient clustering and feature extraction, as well as automatically setting up simulations through the Python API. It is planned to invest development effort into streamlining those processes and integrating them into a new GROMACS tool that will take advantage of the improvements to the API and the analysis tool suite.

3.20 Support for more HADDOCK functionality

HADDOCK currently uses CNS as a backend for a large part of its functionality. It would be advantageous to replace parts of the HADDOCK workflow by an open source backend and GROMACS is the obvious candidate. HADDOCK needs many specific functionalities, in particular for restraints, which are not present in most molecular dynamics package. In addition, HADDOCK use will need a flexible selection syntax. To work towards HADDOCK's use of GROMACS we plan to implement dynamic atom group selections, more restraint functionality and rigid body dynamics.

4 Long-term development plans for HADDOCK

The demands identified during the previous BioExcel iteration were identified and are being addressed with the development of HADDOCK3. HADDOCK3 aims to be standalone and modular with the capability of creating custom workflows and integrating third-party modules/software (e.g. other sampling schemes GROMACS).

HADDOCK2.4 has now been deployed at >850 local installations. Its source code is distributed freely for academic and non-profit users (after registration). The HADDOCK2.4 version is also available via the web interface <https://wenmr.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4> and more than 24,500 users have been registered.

We have been developing HADDOCKv2.5 in parity with v2.4 maintenance. This next version is a port of HADDOCK to Python 3.7+ in order to modernize, optimize, and update the overall code structure, maintaining all previous features.

4.1 HADDOCK2.4 web server

Users mostly interact with the HADDOCK software through the webserver (Figure 1), so we constantly aim towards improving usability and robustness by constantly monitoring the code ourselves and addressing user's feedback and unforeseen problems occurring during its use by external users.

HADDOCK 2.4
@Bonvinlab

WELCOME TO THE UTRECHT BIOMOLECULAR INTERACTION WEB PORTAL >>

Welcome! **HADDOCK** (High Ambiguity Driven protein-protein **DOCK**ing) is an information-driven flexible docking approach for the modeling of biomolecular complexes.

HADDOCK distinguishes itself from ab-initio docking methods in the fact that it encodes information from identified or predicted protein interfaces in ambiguous interaction restraints (AIRs) to drive the docking process. It also allows to define specific unambiguous distance restraints (e.g. from MS cross-links) and supports a variety of other experimental data including NMR residual dipolar couplings, pseudo contact shifts and cryo-EM maps. HADDOCK can deal with a large class of modeling problems including protein-protein, protein-nucleic acids and protein-ligand complexes, including multi-bodies (N>2) assemblies.

HADDOCK is one of the **flagship software** in the EU H2020 BioExcel Center of Excellence for Biomolecular Research.

Register

Submit a new job

See our tutorials

Get Help

Server information

- The access of HADDOCK web server is **free for non-profit users** upon registration.
- Check our usage statistics and world map of users.
- The default HADDOCK **settings used by the server** can be found here.
- A list of **modified amino acids supported by HADDOCK** can be found here.

Figure 1: HADDOCK2.4 web server landing page (<https://wenmr.science.uu.nl>).

HADDOCK is a highly customizable software and has many parameters (500+) that can be tweaked to most modelling needs; however we have observed that this large number of parameters can be overwhelming to many users. To solve this problem, we assign an “EASY” entry level access to each user upon registration in the web interface (Figure 2). In the EASY interface only a limited number of parameters are visible. Users can request higher access (GURU) via their workspace in the web server to access all available HADDOCK parameters

Figure 2: Example of the difference between *GURU* interface (left) and *EASY* interface (right) for the Input of molecules, showing different degrees of complexity.

Jobs can be submitted in 3 different ways: 1) From *scratch* in which the user fills every parameter, 2) from a reproducible *parameter file* generated after the scratch submission and 3) through a simplified *refinement* interface (no docking, only refinement options).

Operation of the HADDOCK web server follows the best Development Operation (DevOps) practices, with CI/CD workflows and Docker deployment, as described in deliverable D1.1. Both the HADDOCK web server as well as the other services, the registration system and the user database are hosted in a dedicated local cluster, which serves as the main entry point: <https://wenmr.science.uu.nl>.

4.1.1 Towards a better User Experience (UX)

We previously reported on how the results are being displayed to the users (regardless of which interface is used) with interactive plots and a web-based molecular visualization of the complexes (see Figure 3). Based on user-feedback we have added more convenient options to download the results. For example, one can download the complete simulation (with a few GB), only the clustered structures, or only the parameter file (that can be used for re-submission). Additionally, there have been optimizations and bug-fixes to the backend routines that are coupled with the result display to provide a more robust display.

Figure 3: HADDOCK result page showing clusters statistics (left) and their visualisation (right). For a live example see: <https://wenmr.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4/run/4242424242/E2A-HPR>

Users can access the web server via three different interfaces, each with a specialized goal, initial submission, replication or refinement. These interfaces are spread across multiple addresses and rely heavily on server-side validation. Recent queries on our Google Analytics have shown that there is room for improvement in user focus and retention of users when using our web server (see section 4.3 about HADDOCK2.5 and the planned new web server).

4.1.2 PDBx/mmCIF export

As a result of our work in BioExcel, the 2.4 version of the HADDOCK server already allows the export of mmCIF, integrative modelling formatted files that combine coordinates with basic information about restraints. These are however only provided on a single model basis. In order to facilitate deposition into the emerging integrative model database (<https://pdb-dev.wwpdb.org>) and hereby catalyse deposition and open sharing of data, we will expand the server capabilities to capture in a single integrative modelling mmCIF file all models,

their statistics and associated data. This work is being done in close collaboration with the integrative modelling task force which we participate in.

(<https://pdb-dev.wwpdb.org/about.html>) and is public and open-source: <https://github.com/haddocking/haddock2mmcif>

4.2 HADDOCK2.4

HADDOCK version 2.4 was released at the end of 2019, as a package for local installation or to be used with the aforementioned web server, which will be operating over the entire duration of BioExcel-2. As described in D1.1, HADDOCK's rolling releases increments upon previously described features such as coarse-graining shape-based docking, etc.

To date 6 updates of HADDOCK2.4 have been released with the most recent one being v2.4-2021.05. The test suite counts to date 39 integration tests representing various scenarios, molecule types, data usage which are meant to test the proper execution and completion of the code and workflow. HADDOCK2.4 also comes with 15 examples that demonstrate its usage for various modelling scenarios.

Some of the most recent additions are new refinement options based on centroid restraints such as described in

- T Neijenhuis, S.C. van Keulen and A.M.J.J. Bonvin. [Interface Refinement of Low-to-Medium Resolution Cryo-EM Complexes using HADDOCK2.4](#). *bioRxiv* (2021). doi:10.1101/2021.06.22.449462

and a novel shape-ligand docking protocol

- P.I. Koukos, M.F. Reau and A.M.J.J. Bonvin. [Shape-restrained modelling of protein-small molecule complexes with HADDOCK](#). *J. Chem. Inf. and Mod.* 6(9) (2021). doi:10.1021/acs.jcim.1c00796

Work is ongoing to extend the support for oligosaccharides and cyclic peptides and develop optimized protocols for their modelling. Besides these we are also developing protocols for membrane protein complexes in which the membrane can be explicitly accounted for since it does provide topological information to guide the docking process. While support for shapes represented by dummy particles is implemented as demonstrated with the recently published shape-restraints docking protocol for protein-ligand complexes, their application to SAXS-based, shape-restrained docking is still being worked on.

4.3 HADDOCK2.5 and its planned new web server

HADDOCK2.5 is a port of HADDOCK2.4 to Python3.7+, including among other optimization of some scheduling routines and better logging information. The functionalities are fully inline with the 2.4 version and any update made to 2.4 is ported to 2.5 (code parity). We plan to make HADDOCK2.5 the official code release in 2022, together with a new version of the HADDOCK web server, which might operate first as devel version with restricted access, in parallel with the current

2.4 production version to gather user feedback before replacing the 2.4 server by the new version (both will provide similar functionalities since the back end 2.4 and 2.5 codes are providing exactly the same functionalities/options). This gradual roll out plan is in line with the HADDOCK development practices as detailed in deliverable D1.1.

For the HADDOCK2.5 web server we are currently developing a newer, modern interface that uses current web development technologies that adapts the single-page application philosophy to the context of our scientific software. The user will be given the following options to submit a run: 1) Upload a parameter file, 2) select from a preset scenario or 3) define all parameters from scratch.

Currently the provided parameter file is a JSON file that the user can edit manually and then submit to the file-interface. At this stage it will be validated. With the new interface we will provide the option for the user to upload a parameter file, which will be read by a JavaScript function that will use the values of the uploaded file to populate the form, in such a way that the interface will act as an embedded parameter file editor. This feature has been requested by users and is not available in the current version of the web server. These changes will provide the users with a much friendlier, less error-prone and more productive manner of verifying and modifying their configuration before re-running a previous simulation.

In the current 2.4 server interface we suggest optimal parameters for a given simulation based on the molecule type identified in the system. These optimal values are based on our own observations and benchmarks. We will take advantage of the new interface and provide the users with preset scenarios based on the most relevant topics we observe in the user support channels (ask.bioexcel.eu) such as, for example, ab initio, small molecule or glycan docking. The current refinement interface will be replaced by such presets, which will simplify the server interface and increase its maintainability. The interface will read files analogous to the aforementioned parameter files that were manually built by us, using the more optimal values for each scenario. This approach will provide the users a more comprehensive and robust set of parameters so that the software can be utilized to its full extent.

Lastly, users can choose to build a run from scratch, similarly to what it is done for the current v2.4, selecting each parameter according to its own research question. Creating simulation setups in this manner will expose users to either the full options of HADDOCK in case of *GURU*-level users or to simplified views for *EASY* users. We also aim to improve usability by improving the parameter description tooltips and adding relevant links to the Best Practice Guide (<https://www.bonvinlab.org/software/bpg/>).

HADDOCK 2.4 **DEVELOPMENT VERSION**
@Bonvinlab

Home HADDOCK2.4 About Register Submit Submit file Activity User profile Login

WELCOME TO THE UTRECHT BIOMOLECULAR INTERACTION WEB PORTAL >>

HADDOCK parameter submission

To begin, please choose one option

Random restraints

Job name *

name-of-your-run

Molecule input

Restraints

Parameters

POWERED BY

This work is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 projects EOSC-hub (grant number 777536) and BioExcel (grant numbers 023839 and 675726) and by a computing grant from NWO-ENW (project number 2019.053).

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Terms of use | Privacy

Figure 4: Prototype HADDOCK submission page as a single-step submission with option to upload a parameter file, choose a preset or start for scratch.

4.4 HADDOCK3

We continue developing HADDOCK3, representing a ground-up rework of the previous HADDOCK2.x code to pursue extensibility, modularization, testability and documentation. In HADDOCK3, we are rebuilding both the Python shell and CNS core code, adding new features while porting HADDOCK2.x functionalities in a modularized fashion. We provide the HADDOCK3 official repository at <http://github.com/haddock/haddock3>, where we have the daily development progressions, discussions, development roadmaps, etc. (see section 4.4.3). The first HADDOCK3 Alpha version released in May 2020¹ is still available for the record. Since that release we have improved HADDOCK3's codebase tremendously and the daily-builds in the main branch should be used to reference the state of the project.

Currently, HADDOCK3 can generate topologies with CNS, perform rigid body sampling, semi-flexible refinement, water refinement, EM refinement, clustering with FCC, score models and also contains third party integrations with other docking software such as LightDock and gdock. Modular workflows can be created by rearranging modules (see section 4.4.1)

We are intensively working towards releasing the first stable and production-ready version - v3.0.0. Maintaining BioExcel open-science practices, the progress of HADDOCK3 developments is constantly updated, and anyone can follow it² (see also section 4.4.3).

The following sections explain in detail our development strategy and current achievements on HADDOCK3.

4.4.1 Modular workflows

Our primary motivation to develop HADDOCK3 is to be able to create modular simulation workflows that can be assembled on-demand by the user and according to the project needs. This level of modularity is the most significant contrast with the previous HADDOCK2.x version in which a static workflow was executing sequentially the rigid body docking (it0), the semi-flexible refinement (it1), and the final solvated refinement (itw). Instead, the HADDOCK3 framework allows flexibility to define the simulation protocol, facilitating the creation of project-specific workflows, allowing skipping unnecessary stages, and also introducing third-party software components if needed. This redesign will directly benefit our efforts towards exascale computing since we are building this new version considering a large-scale execution, removing the number of files generated, optimizing the steps taken, avoiding executing unnecessary steps, etc.

The following are examples of possible future workflow scenarios:

1. sampling (previous it0) with third party docking software (e.g. LightDock) + flexible refinement with HADDOCK (previous it1) + solvated refinement with HADDOCK

¹ <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3/releases/tag/v3.0.alpha2>

² <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3/milestone/1>

2. sampling and refinement with HADDOCK + solvated refinement with GROMACS or openMM
3. skip the docking stage and only perform some flexible refinement (various scenarios possible) with HADDOCK
4. restrained docking with HADDOCK + clustering + selection of top clusters + flexible refinement + flexible refinement round 2 + clustering + scoring

In scenario 1) HADDOCK could be replaced by other docking software that better explores of the interaction space in the initial docking stage while switching to HADDOCK for the flexible refinement,

Scenario 2) replaces the water refinement of HADDOCK with novel molecular dynamics strategies using GROMACS or openMM, possibly for distinguishing near-native from wrong model as recently demonstrated in our article:

- Z. Jandova, A.V. Vargiu and A.M.J.J. Bonvin. [Native or non-native protein-protein docking models? Molecular dynamics to the rescue.](#) J. Chem. Theo. and Comp. 17, 5944–5954 (2021). doi:10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00336

Scenario 3) could corresponds to a refinement protocol applied to large cryo-EM structures with low to medium resolution as described in:

- T Neijenhuis, S.C. van Keulen and A.M.J.J. Bonvin. [Interface Refinement of Low-to-Medium Resolution Cryo-EM Complexes using HADDOCK2.4.](#) bioRxiv (2021) doi:2021.06.22.449462.

Scenario 4) would be a standard HADDOCK docking scenario using ambiguous restraints but with clustering after the initial stage and two rounds of refinement of the selected models from the top clusters.

The end of section 4.4.2 explains how we achieve such modularity and what is the current user interface to configure it.

4.4.2 Most relevant implementation strategies

We divided the new Python-shell architecture managing HADDOCK3 functionalities into independent building blocks, such as: non-variable physical parameters, command-line interfaces, plug-ins, the CNS code for the actual simulations, and most importantly, the functional modules configuring for each calculation stage.

Thus, we can manage each of these blocks and blocks' pieces independently, adding or removing them without breaking the remaining of the software. Also, whenever possible, we are reimplementing some external libraries to reduce HADDOCK3's dependencies on community-based Python libraries (outside the Python standard library) as these tend to be discontinued in time or evolve in unpredictable ways. Thus, increasing long term maintainability. The following paragraphs and figures briefly describe HADDOCK's Python-shell building blocks.

Figure 5: Structure and organization of the HADDOCK3 source directory. All code functionalities are stored under these main categories

The **command-line infrastructure (CLI)** holds the architecture needed to implement command-line interfaces. Currently, the main `haddock3` command exists, but we can implement new CLIs quickly if required.

The **CNS core code** is being ported and modularized from HADDOCK2.x and will reside in a specific folder within HADDOCK3. General CNS code will serve several simulation modules, thus avoiding code repetition. In contrast, module-specific CNS code will reside within each simulation module folder.

The **non-variable physical parameters** exist in a separate module inside the HADDOCK3 code. The core developers can modify these parameters if needed, but these are not accessible to the users because they represent physical constraints.

The **plug-ins module** contains all functionalities outside core simulations that extend the user-friendliness of HADDOCK3. For example, restarting a run from a specified step and improving the configuration file flexibility. These are stored in the `gear` folder.

The **libs** folder stores general functionalities that serve the whole of the package. For example, I/O, small parsing operations, multiprocessing routines, etc.

The **simulation modules** are subroutines within HADDOCK3 with the instructions to run each module per se. Examples of simulation modules are rigid-body docking, flexible refinement, FCC clustering, scoring, and representation. We can add or remove these subroutines without breaking any functionalities of the others. HADDOCK3's own simulation routines are based on CNS but, here, and as referred to in section 4.4.1, HADDOCK3 Workflow Manager can incorporate third-party libraries for any particular operation. Currently, we have implemented

bridge routines to operate with Lightdock³ and gdock (unpublished), two docking software. These are fully integrated into our input/output unified managing system.

Figure 6: The code structure for HADDOCK3 modules follows a homogeneous pattern facilitating and guiding the incorporation of new modules.

A primary novelty of HADDOCK3 is its flexibility to assemble a pipeline of simulation modules according to the user/project's needs, in direct contrast to HADDOCK2.x where a rigid protocol exists. See our explanation in section 4.4.1. To achieve this pipelining capacity, we have developed a dedicated input/output system that homogenizes the I/O interfaces of the modules. Thus, the only requirement to assemble two modules is that the output of the first conceptually (scientifically) matches the input of the next module. Another significant difference from the previous versions is that we can repeat modules in the pipeline. To obtain this functionality, we developed a dedicated and simplified configuration file formatting. Our new configuration file follows simplified standards with enhanced functionalities for HADDOCK3 specific requirements (Figure 7).

³ Jiménez-García, B. et al. LightDock: a new multi-scale approach to protein–protein docking. *Bioinformatics* 34, 49–55 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btx555>

```

1 #
=====
2 # Rigid-body docking example
3
4 # directory where results will be saved
5 run_dir = "run1"
6
7 # source structures
8 molecules = [
9     "../data/1a2k_l_u.pdb",
10    "../data/1a2k_r_u.pdb"
11    ]
12
13 # an empty lines must follow multiline lists|
14
15 [topoaa]
16 autohis = true # comments are allowed
17
18 [rigidbody] # also in headers
19 ambig = '../data/1a2k_ti.tbl'# event without spaces
20 sampling = 20
21
22 [seletopclusts]
23 top_cluster = [1, 2, 3, 4]
24 top_models = 4
25
26 [flexref]
27 ambig = '../data/1a2k_ti.tbl'
28 cool1_steps = 500
29
30 [seletopclusts]
31 top_cluster = [1, 2, 3, 4]
32 top_models = 4
33
34 [mdref]
35 ambig = '../data/1a2k_ti.tbl'
36 cool1_steps = 10
37
38 [clustfcc]
39 contact_distance_cutoff = 5.0
40 fraction_cutoff = 0.6
41 threshold = 4

```

Figure 7: Example of the new HADDOCK3 configuration file.

The first parameters define the general arguments that are always required and are agnostic to the workflow itself. Then, each workflow stage is defined by a bracket title - **[topoaa]** for topology generation. Below each stage title are the state-specific parameters. Contrarily to HADDOCK2 where the configuration file required all possible parameters, in HADDOCK3 only those parameters the user wants to modify with respect to the defaults are required. Stages can be repeated as exemplified by **[seletopclusts]**. The order the workflow executes the stages is defined by the order stages are configured in the configuration file - do the configuration file also reads sequentially.

4.4.3 Developers and users community

In HADDOCK3, we are committed to engaging with the community of developers and users and have our work open to the public for sharing, mentoring, and

developing purposes. The HADDOCK3 repository has several sections where users and developers can interact with us:

In the **Projects tab**⁴, we have a Kanban-like interface where everyone can follow up live on the project's development. There, we feature subsections related to "enhancements", "new features", "bug triage", and "documentation writing". These Kanban-like interfaces are also valuable for new developers to interact with us because they can see which activities are pending for developing and can engage with us where they can provide best input.

In the **Pull Request tab**⁵, every code addition to the repository passes through a revision process by the core team; but this revision process is open to everyone who wishes to participate and follow. Hence, we adhere to best practices for team software development. Likewise, the roadmap of development is tracked in the **Issues tab**⁶, where bugs, feature requests are registered.

A new GitHub **Discussion tab**⁷ is a forum-like platform within the repository where developers and users can communicate and discuss the project's needs. There, we already host several discussions that have resulted in positive implementations.

Finally, the development of the future version 3.0.0 stable release (that is, production ready) can also be followed live on our GitHub repository⁸.

Moreover, we plan to use the new HADDOCK3's code implementations as references for scientific software engineering and good modularity practices, extensibility, and tests by writing and deploying tutorials and explanatory documents on our group's webpage.

4.4.4 Toward efficient HPC running mode and exascale

Reaching Exascale, which will be required for large scale simulation of for example interactomes or drug screening campaigns, will require efficient workflows and submission machinery. The main focus of this effort so far is related to the use of HADDOCK v2.4, but we will also investigate the potential of tackling this challenge using the modular v3.0. While the compute intensive parts of the HADDOCK workflow are a perfect example of embarrassingly parallel execution, the pre- and post-processing steps are of sequential nature. The compute intensive parts are also generating a large amount of rather small files, which can stress both network and filesystem. For this reason and in response to user requests we have already redesigned the internal job handling machinery, adding options to send self-contained jobs that can run fully locally on node and only return data upon

⁴ <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3/projects>

⁵ <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3/pulls>

⁶ <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3/issues>

⁷ <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3/discussions>

⁸ <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3/milestone/1>

completion, in a similar way as what is currently done in grid submission mode. The I/O bottleneck has been investigated in D1.2, for which we created a benchmark of 1M files and evaluated the time necessary to extract information from this huge volume of files, mimicking an exa-scale scenario.

Furthermore we have developed a new scheduler prototype capable of handling very large volumes of simulations, custom built to optimize the HADDOCK execution (<https://github.com/haddock/haddock-pilot>). In the default running mode HADDOCK starts locally on a login/master node and takes responsibility for submitting the workloads to the local batch system (or grid submission). For large scale simulations, this might generate a very high load on the queuing system scheduler, which has to handle thousands of submissions. Building on the established Pilot Job abstraction pattern⁹, the new pilot scheduler, the pilots are started on all allocated nodes in an HPC system through a single submission to the batch system. Each allocated node will run the pilot that will pull in and process HADDOCK workloads locally, minimising network communication during the computations and only returning the data once the run has completed. The pilots will automatically stop once the work units have all been processed.

4.5 Virtualization

HADDOCK has been containerized via Docker and Singularity technologies, with recipes maintained in an internal repository (as the containers do contain third party software which cannot be freely redistributed, e.g. CNS). A Docker container was built on top of the latest PyCOMPSs container as a technological test linked with WP2. We expect such containers will be key to scaling up computations on HPC resources toward exascale interactome modelling. We are implementing the most efficient way of running those on HPC resources. This virtualisation will also facilitate HADDOCK's usage on local resources by end users.

5 Long term development plans for QM/MM with CP2K and GROMACS

5.1 Development of scalable GROMACS-CP2K interface for QM/MM

Mechanistic insights into the catalytic action of enzymes is needed to understand how these proteins have evolved to mediate chemical reactivity. Also, for improving enzymes or designing new ones, detailed understanding of the underlying reaction mechanism is essential.

Because time and spatial resolutions are difficult to access experimentally, *hybrid QM/MM simulation techniques* are the methods of choice to investigate enzyme

⁹ M. Turilli, M. Santcross, S. Jha (2018): **A Comprehensive Perspective on Pilot-Job Systems**. *ACM Computing Surveys* 51(2):43 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3177851>

reactivity; in which a small part of the system is modelled with a suitable level of ab initio or density functional theory, while the remainder is modelled with a molecular mechanics force field.

However, despite the simplicity of the QM/MM concept, their application was restricted to a small group of specialized users typically using in-house codes.

To unlock the power of QM/MM simulations to the whole biomolecular simulation community, we developed an interface between GROMACS and CP2K that, in contrast to previous interfaces, supports QM/MM calculations under periodic boundary conditions, and provide the user with new user-friendly tools to investigate enzyme mechanisms.

The further developments will enable and accelerate the adoption of DFT and semi-empirical methods available in CP2K for biomolecular modelling & simulation using hybrid QM/MM simulation. This roadmap reflects the project to develop and support the new GROMACS/CP2K interface, which should have more wide-spread availability and uptake in the community.

5.1.1 Prototyping using existing implementation of QM/MM interface in GROMACS

The first prototype of the GROMACS/CP2K interface for performing fully-periodic QM/MM simulations will be implemented within the old QM/MM interface of GROMACS. Although that interface will be deprecated in future GROMACS releases, it serves as the basis for data exchange and interconnection between CP2K and GROMACS. Through static linking against `libcp2k` we will use the prototype interface for CP2K code optimization and testing (see section 5.2) in parallel with the development and refactoring of a totally new interface framework that will be based on the future *MDModules* framework of GROMACS, see subsection 5.1.2.

5.1.2 Modularization of the interface within GROMACS MDModules framework

Modularization of the QM/MM routines is important to maintain flexibility for linking GROMACS with quantum chemistry programs other than CP2K. Maximum flexibility will be achieved by developing an extension module within the planned *MDModules* framework, which enables plugging functionality into the GROMACS core MD engine through a single interface.

The relevant CP2K routines including any optimizations introduced as part of the work described in section 5.2 will remain inside the CP2K library (`libcp2k`), which is compiled separately and either linked to dynamically when building GROMACS with the new interface module included or incorporated directly into the resulting GROMACS executable through static linking.

5.1.3 Extending parallelization of the CP2K interface for efficient usage of existing GROMACS capabilities

In order to pave the way for ambitious GROMACS/CP2K-based QM/MM simulations on Exascale HPC resources, development of this interface will consider in detail design choices regarding parallel execution, and in particular how the existing domain decomposition within GROMACS can be made to optimally make use of MPI-parallel execution of CP2K routines, as the latter is crucial for speeding up the computationally costly QM/MM energy plus gradient calculations.

MPI sub-communicators, which can be passed to relevant CP2K routines as an alternative to using all MPI ranks (MPI_COMM_WORLD), will be employed for flexible parallelism, for example this scheme will be beneficial in ensemble simulation methods. The efficient passing of atomic coordinates and return of QM/MM forces between GROMACS and CP2K within the existing GROMACS domain decomposition will also be taken into account.

The interface will be designed and developed iteratively, with decisions affecting performance and scalability guided by analysis of their impact for a variety of biomolecular systems in addition to the project's QM/MM use cases and on multiple hardware platforms including CPU-only and CPU+GPU nodes.

The interface test cases will exercise the interface in a variety of scenarios spanning a wide range of community uses to highlight potential problems and performance bottlenecks, e.g. in dealing with multiple QM regions, inter-timestep wavefunction handling etc., resulting in a more performance, scalable and robust implementation.

5.1.4 Improvements to the GROMACS/CP2K interface user-experience

In order to respond to user needs we are planning to continue improvements in both installation procedures and general workflow of the QM/MM simulations. Many of the widely-used DFT methods will be available through the interface directly, accompanied by the parameter sets tested for the biomolecular systems on the basis of the previously developed Bioexcel-2 benchmark suite. These efforts will include support of hybrid DFT functionals such as *B3LYP* and *PBE0* that are the most used nowadays in studying enzymatic reactions, support for dispersion corrections, MP2 *ab initio* method and wider choice of basis sets.

Build and installation procedure of the GROMACS/CP2K interface will be improved by implementing automatic frameworks with specialized software such as EasyBuild. We will also provide pre-compiled Docker containers with the interface for testing and training purposes. That will allow better uptake of the latest developments by the community as well as widen the range of HPC centers which will provide access to our software.

5.1.5 QM/MM interface API to allow usage of other QM packages

After the initial release of the GROMACS/CP2K interface we expect that other QM package developers might want to use our interface for linking their software with GROMACS. In order to simplify such efforts all reusable parts of our CP2K interface, such as topology processor, will be made available for other developers as standardized API within *MDModules*. We are planning to support external developments both for extensions of CP2K interface and other QM packages

5.1.6 Support of semi-empirical and DFTB methods in the QM/MM interface

Semi-empirical methods as well as DFTB have become more popular in the biomolecular modelling community due to lower computational effort needed to perform such simulations in comparison to conventional DFT. Often these methods are used to perform preliminary calculations in order to quickly check hypotheses. Our efforts will be focused on allowing current semi-empirical methods from CP2K to be used effectively within the developed interface. For that case we will implement a fully periodic QM/MM scheme on the basis of the existing GEEP approach for semi-empirical, DFTB and xTB methods available in the CP2K. In addition, we will consider extending QM/MM interface with support for external libraries performing semi-empirical calculations, such as the DFTB+ package.

5.1.7 Support of excited state methods and excited state dynamics

To study reactions that happen in the excited states of the molecules, such as in photo-synthetic centers and fluorescent proteins, fast and robust approaches for describing those processes should be available. To use such a method as time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) that is implemented in the CP2K package we need to introduce additional features into the GROMACS/CP2K interface. First feature which will be implemented is the state tracking procedure in order to check the current status of the system, as excited-state reactions are often preceded through a series of transitions between different states. Second feature which will be implemented is the surface-hopping algorithm, which will allow excited state dynamics to follow a particular path of the processes and track non-radiative channels of system deactivation.

5.1.8 Support of multiple time-stepping integration scheme for QM/MM simulations

Both GROMACS and CP2K packages have an ability to perform force evaluation with different time-steps. That scheme allows evaluation of some energies and forces terms less frequently than others, thereby greatly improving performance. We will investigate the ways of incorporating that approach into the QM/MM interface. In addition, we will perform the systematic performance evaluation of multiple time-stepping simulations approach on a wide-range of biomolecular systems, using the benchmark suite, described in the following part 5.2.

5.2 Optimization of CP2K for QM/MM through GROMACS-CP2K interface

CP2K optimization work planned in D1.3 – *Updated software roadmaps* and already completed during BioExcel-2 has been reported in D1.4 – *Project release of core applications*. Since then we have expanded the BioExcel QM/MM benchmark suite based on best practices developed through our Use Case work and on community priorities, for example by including higher theory level QM treatment in the form of hybrid functionals (PBE0 and B3LYP).

The benchmark suite was used to perform systematic profiling on a range of architectures including Intel (Broadwell) and AMD (EPYC Zen2) multicore CPUs, and NVIDIA GPUs (V100) using a protocol developed to factor out initialization costs and provide a clear picture of production run performance based on short benchmark proxies. We developed an auxiliary software tool to automate postprocessing and visualization of large amounts of profiling data in order to facilitate comparison of absolute performance and parallel scaling bottlenecks. The benchmarks used enabled key QM treatment parameters such as the level of theory (GGA vs hybrid functionals), number of atoms treated using QM for a given problem, and the size of the QM cell to be varied independently, allowing their individual effects on performance and scaling to be accurately assessed and optimization work to be prioritized depending on its effect on targeted usage and likely benefit to users.

The sections below provide updates to the corresponding sections in D1.3 in light of this prioritization and in light of the expected hardware and software trends in coming years.

5.2.1 Optimization of GEEP subroutines

The CP2K subroutines that compute the long-range electrostatic QM/MM forces and energies using the Gaussian Expansion of the Electrostatic Potential (GEEP) algorithm, which are used by GROMACS through its interface to CP2K, were planned in D1.3 to be optimized for performance. As described in D1.4, OpenMP parallelization was added directly to a number of GEEP subroutines.

Since D1.3 a new high performance-oriented “*grid*” package has been developed within CP2K. This package provides an API for CP2K Fortran code that needs to perform collocation and/or integration, i.e. map operators between their Gaussian-basis matrix and real-space multigrid representations. It is now used by CP2K’s core Quickstep functionality. The *grid* API is written in C, can be built standalone from CP2K, and provides a separation of concerns between computational chemists developing CP2K, who should specify collocate/integrate tasks using the API, and performance engineers, who can develop alternative versions of the “back end” code that performs the actual required underlying computations in order to be highly performant on a diverse range of hardware architectures and programming models, such as OpenMP, CUDA, and HIP.

The GEEP subroutines should be modified to take advantage of the new *grid* API for grid collocation and integration operations. This will not only enable more comprehensive OpenMP parallelization, but also pave the way for CUDA and HIP-based offloading of GEEP. That is a critical long-term benefit not only because it complements the current hardware platforms used by GROMACS users, who will utilize the QM/MM interface to CP2K, but also given the increasing availability and reliance in HPC systems on accelerators from NVIDIA and, increasingly, AMD.

The grid API will continue to receive long term active development from the CP2K developers in order to implement and optimize back-end code targeting future CPUs and GPUs as it is core to performance of CP2K overall, hence tying QM/MM subroutines into this framework is the ideal way to provide sustainable long-term multi-architecture support and performance optimization benefit for our user community, even beyond the lifetime of current BioExcel funding.

5.2.2 Improvement of Quickstep DFT load balancing for biomolecular QM/MM

The systematic benchmark profiling described in 5.2 has shown that, for a range of biomolecular systems simulated on various hardware architectures and using parameters we have come to consider representative of best practice production runs, the Quickstep load imbalance previously highlighted in D1.3 is actually not a particular concern for optimisation. This is in part because the inter-timestep configurational change is small enough such that wavefunction reuse and extrapolation is already sufficiently efficient. Hence, for the long-term CP2K QM/MM roadmap we have strongly deprioritised the previous optimisation target of improving Quickstep load balancing described in D1.3.

5.2.3 Optimization of CP2K subroutines and DBCSR GPU acceleration identified by performance analysis of the GROMACS-CP2K interface

The systematic benchmark profiling described in 5.2 that we performed since formulation of D1.3 revealed two leading scaling bottlenecks.

First, for a range of biomolecular systems simulated on various hardware architectures using parameters we consider representative of best practice production runs, some plane wave subroutines, predominantly *pw_integral_ab*, which computes the integral for two functions in plane wave basis representation, actually grew their fractional contribution to execution time on larger numbers of cores, thereby becoming the dominant bottleneck to parallel scaling. This can be traced back to calls to Kahan summation of arrays. These may constitute an exceedingly cautious approach to guaranteeing precision, which could be relaxed in the vast majority of cases, which should strongly benefit parallel scaling efficiency for user community's usage.

Second, when using hybrid functionals such as PBE0 and B3LYP, the computation of four_centre HFX integrals and derivatives dominates runtime. These intense computations are currently not performed by CP2K, but by calls to the external

library *libint*. The CP2K developer team is however working to implement computation of these integrals and derivatives inside their own GPU-accelerated DBCSR library instead, which will enable them to be offloaded onto GPUs through CUDA or, increasingly, HIP, and should also reduce memory requirements for a given accuracy. This approach is promising in the long term for the use of hybrid functionals and other higher theory level QM methods for biomolecular QM/MM simulation, as these particularly intensive calculations will be able to be offloaded to increasingly powerful GPUs available in many HPC systems.

Finally, in D1.3 we envisaged incorporating results from our biomolecular QM/MM benchmarks into a then novel machine learning-based procedure for generating optimized small-matrix multiplication kernel parameters used by the DBCSR library. Systematic benchmark profiling performed since then, however, showed that the most significant bottlenecks in absolute performance and parallel scaling were not due to existing calls already offloading matrix computations to DBCSR, hence we have deprioritised optimising these kernels further. It is feasible that after more relevant optimizations described above and/or increased reliance on DBCSR generally in future CP2K releases, this optimization target becomes relevant again, however this would depend on future assessments.

5.3 Implementation of efficient optimizers and transition path methods in GROMACS

Although enzymes accelerate chemical reactions by orders of magnitude, their turn-over rate is usually far too slow to occur spontaneously in QM/MM simulations. Therefore, *biasing approaches* are needed to investigate enzyme catalysis. The development will focus on providing users with tools that can automatically locate transition states on exascale hardware.

In accordance with user requests, we have decided to postpone actions on this part to later stages and rather prioritize the targets mentioned in section 5.1. Our aim is to allow usage of existing enhanced sampling methods within GROMACS, such as Umbrella Sampling and Accelerated Weight Histogram (AWH) dynamics, for studying enzymatic reactions with the QM/MM interface.

5.3.1 Update L-BFGS optimizer in GROMACS

The development of the new optimizers will focus on finding stationary points on the potential energy surfaces of large biological systems. For that purpose, the existing optimizers in GROMACS will be upgraded. In particular, the existing L-BFGS (limited Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno) optimizer will be updated to work efficiently within modern versions of GROMACS, using C++14 as a standard. The new L-BFGS will support Domain Decomposition within the massively parallel MPI implementations of GROMACS.

5.3.2 Micro-iterations for multiscale systems optimization.

To increase the computational efficiency of QM/MM optimizations, the number of computationally demanding quantum chemistry calculations should be minimized. The latter can be achieved within so-called micro-iterations schemes that alternate between the optimization of a few degrees of freedom at the higher level of theory (QM) and the optimization of a much larger number of degrees of freedom at the lower level of theory (MM).

To provide users with more powerful optimizers for QM/MM, a micro-iteration scheme will be implemented based on the improved L-BFGS optimizer (see subsection 5.3.1). This optimizer will be used for both the global macro-cycles at the MM level and for the micro-iterations of the QM subsystem.

5.3.3 Implementation of Nudged Elastic Band method (NEB) for optimizations of transition states in GROMACS.

For small isolated systems, transition states separating the reactants from the products can be optimized efficiently if the Hessian is available. In contrast, for large systems with periodic boundary conditions, the Hessian is not readily available. Therefore, transition state search algorithms for large systems need to rely on non-Hessian methods.

Because Chain-of-states methods do not require the Hessian, and are easy to parallelize, they are ideally suited for finding transition states in enzymes on exascale hardware.

A popular chain-of-states approach, the *Nudge Elastic Band* (NEB) method, will be implemented in GROMACS. In this approach, multiple geometries connecting the reactant and product minima are generated through interpolation and optimized individually with harmonic restraints between successive geometries.

The new NEB implementation will be based on existing functionality in GROMACS for performing simulations of multiple coupled systems (i.e. *mdrun -multi*), which provides the infrastructure to perform the optimization of each member of the transition path ensemble on a separate group of processors and communicate the information for applying the harmonic restraint between the members.

The optimization of the individual members will be performed within the micro-iteration framework (subsection 5.3.2), using the upgraded L-BFGS optimizer (subsection 5.3.1).

6 Long-term development plans for PMX

While GROMACS provides a robust molecular dynamics engine providing a reliable and efficient back-end for carrying out alchemical free energy calculations, the specialized pre-processing required for such calculations can be provided by means of the pmx software package.

Currently, pmx allows for the setup and subsequent analysis of amino acid and nucleic acid mutations, as well as ligand modifications. The pmx tools can be called from the command line or via an online webserver (<http://pmx.mpibpc.mpg.de/>), which supports amino and nucleic acid mutations.

In addition to supporting the structure and topology preparation for the subsequent simulations, pmx aims to provide a full free energy calculation workflow. The modular nature of the workflow elements would allow for a flexible incorporation of GROMACS/pmx into academic and industrial pipelines.

In tandem with the pmx development, changes to the GROMACS code are necessary to provide state-of-the-art functionality for free energy calculations. For that purpose a softcore potential functionality is implemented to allow for reliable non-equilibrium free energy calculations.

6.1 Plans for the core code and usability

6.1.1 Python3

The original pmx version was based on the Python 2 programming language, for which support by Python developers ended in 2020. It was therefore one of the major goals for the pmx code development to transition all of the classes, modules and scripts to Python 3.

During the period of BioExcel-2, while gradually adapting the code to Python 3, two versions of pmx co-existed in the GitHub repository: “*master*” branch¹⁰ based on Python 2 and “*develop*” branch¹¹ based on Python 3. This transition process started in 2020.

In 2021 we have now fully ported pmx core functionalities to Python 3. The remaining Python 2 code to be ported comprises the supporting functionalities for free energy calculation planning and pmx-webserver. The last parts will be finalized by the end of 2021 completing the pmx transition to Python 3.

6.1.2 Conda

To allow for a convenient cross-platform installation and use of pmx, we are planning to make pmx available via the Conda packaging system, as already

¹⁰ <https://github.com/deGrootLab/pmx>

¹¹ <https://github.com/deGrootLab/pmx/tree/develop>

utilized by WP2 for BioExcel Building Blocks. The long term goal is to distribute pmx via the BioConda channel. Early work on Conda packaging of pmx's development version has already been performed by WP2 in BioConda¹² - this work will be aligned towards official pmx releases.

Currently, installation instructions¹³ have been prepared for a quick and convenient setup of pmx using Python's `pip install`.

6.1.3 Further modularization

While the pmx library is built in a modular manner comprising classes for handling molecular structures and topologies, the alchemical hybrid structure/topology setup is provided as a set of specialized scripts that utilize the pmx infrastructure. In some applications, for example large scale mutational scans or custom free energy workflows, it is preferable to avoid calling external scripts.

This can be circumvented by implementing the functionality of the currently available setup as independent classes of pmx. Further, it would allow the users to easily call separate modules of those classes, allowing creation of more specialized, user tailored workflows.

By the end of 2021 we successfully built a modular structure for protein, nucleic acid and ligand modification handling. The calculation analysis has also been modularized allowing for an efficient incorporation in custom workflows. Additional classes for the overall free energy calculation setup and simulation submission to the cluster have been created. Further improvement on these classes will be one of the important objectives for the future pmx development, as they will allow building complete free energy workflows.

Having finalized the transition to Python3 and modularized the core functionalities of pmx, we are planning the major release for the first quarter of 2022. At this point the current "master" branch, that is based on Python2, will be retired and the current "develop" branch will replace the current "master".

6.2 Mutation libraries

6.2.1 New libraries

pmx provides hybrid structure/topology generation for arbitrary amino and nucleic acid mutations. This is achieved by means of pre-generated atom mapping schemes between the residues. The sets of these mappings constitute mutation libraries, which are force field dependent. With the continuous development of new force fields, it is important to provide updated mutation libraries as well. One of the goals for pmx development is to further automate the mutation library generation procedure and provide a timely update of these libraries once the new versions of force fields are released. With the latest pmx development we also

¹² https://anaconda.org/bioconda/pmx_biobb

¹³ <https://github.com/deGrootLab/pmx#installation>

provide support to the new generation protein force fields (Amber14sb and Charmm36m).

6.2.2 Automated tests for mutation libraries

This is a goal closely related to section 6.2.1. Currently, every newly generated mutation library is tested in a generated topology for consistency with a set of scripts that are not part of the main pmx library. The goal is to incorporate the testing routines into pmx and enable an easy-to-use automated execution of these tests for every newly created mutation library.

6.2.3 Unified amino acid and DNA mutation libraries

Currently, the mutation libraries are separated based on the biomolecule type: amino acids and nucleic acids have different libraries, hence different force fields. In principle, this separation is not necessary, as a protein force field with the incorporated amino acid mutations can be combined with the DNA force field with the nucleic acid mutations. Such merging of the mutation libraries, although it seems to be natural, requires some internal reorganization of pmx. The unified amino acid and DNA mutation libraries can only be pursued after fully transitioning pmx to Python3.

Having finished the transition of the core pmx functionalities to Python3 have allowed generating the versions of Amber and Charmm force fields comprising both amino acid and DNA mutations. With all the functionality already in place, the next step in further completing mutational libraries will be creating various combinations of the compatible protein and DNA force fields.

6.3 Features

6.3.1 Amino acid protonation

Estimating free energy changes upon amino acid protonation/deprotonation (pKa differences) is a frequently requested pmx feature. From the perspective of alchemical calculations, protonation can be viewed as a particular mutation of appearing/disappearing hydrogen bound to an amino acid. In fact, the pmx mutation libraries already allow probing protonation changes for some amino acids. This feature, however, has only been probed against experimental data for several instances. Furthermore, the calculation of the proton annihilation is necessarily associated with the undesired change in the overall system charge.

While there are methods to conserve charge of the simulation box throughout such a simulation, it is important to develop an automated setup for this procedure. All in all, for pmx to provide robust predictions of the pKa shifts, it is necessary to implement this specific simulation setup and validate it against experimental data.

By the end of 2021 we have prototyped the use of alchemical pmx based methods to calculate pKa shifts in the context of protein stability. Having the first proof-of-principle result we are aiming to develop an automated setup to allow for a systematic assessment of pKa changes in proteins and ligands.

6.3.2 Post-translational modifications

Amino acid mutations representing post-translational modifications is another frequently requested pmx feature. To implement this, it is necessary to develop a flexible generation of arbitrary mutations in a library.

This functionality is in part comparable to ligand modifications, where alchemical morphs between arbitrary compounds are created. In addition, the incorporation of post-translational modifications requires extending the core pmx responsible for identifying and handling entries in the mutation libraries. These changes comprise a long term goal for pmx development.

6.3.3 Covalent modifications

Alchemical bond breaking is advised against in the standard free energy calculation setups. There are situations, however, where it is not possible to avoid annihilating a bond, e.g. proline involving mutations.

In these cases, carefully designed topology generations may prove it feasible to allow the disappearance of a bond, e.g. the pmx “*develop*” branch already readily allows proline mutations that involve ring opening/closure and thus covalent bond breaking/formation. The adaptation of such schemes in more general scenarios requires further exploration. A long term goal is for pmx to support at least for some common alchemical covalent modifications.

6.3.4 Workflows

pmx is already capable of generating input for various alchemical modifications, i.e. all the necessary preparation and pre-processing. At the start of BioExcel-2, the next step of the actual free energy calculation itself was left fully for the user to carry out. One of the main goals for pmx development is to provide a set of workflows that would allow a convenient simulation setup using the readily available hybrid structure/topology input. The workflows will cover both the equilibrium and non-equilibrium free energy calculation protocols using pmx as the input generator and GROMACS as the simulation engine.

Since 2021 pmx has included classes for building a free energy workflow into its “*develop*” branch. An illustrative case for the relative protein-ligand binding affinity calculations has been developed and is provided to the users in the form of a tutorial which can be quickly adapted to the custom needs of a particular project. With the main classes for the workflow construction in place, the next steps involve development of workflows for protein mutations, DNA mutations and absolute protein-ligand binding free energy calculations.

6.3.5 Absolute binding free energy calculations

Relative protein-ligand binding affinity calculations are readily supported by pmx. These calculations allow evaluating binding free energy differences for ligand libraries composed of chemically similar compounds. Conceptually, the next major challenge is to enable binding affinity estimation for any arbitrary compound

without the need to construct and explore a library of similar molecules. This approach requires computing absolute protein-ligand binding free energy.

We have now demonstrated that such calculations are possible to achieve with the pmx/GROMACS software and obtained accurate estimates on a large number of diverse systems.¹⁴ The future steps in this direction will involve further development of absolute protein-ligand binding affinity calculation workflows for a convenient setup in high throughput drug discovery pipelines.

6.3.6 Softcore function implementation in GROMACS

While the pmx software is agnostic to the free energy calculation methodology, throughout numerous investigations we have observed that the methods based on non-equilibrium sampling of the alchemical space offer many advantages over the other approaches. The efficient and robust use of non-equilibrium methods, however, required reformulation of the soft-coring function for the non-bonded interactions in molecular dynamics simulations.

We have worked in a close collaboration with the GROMACS team and MPCDF (Garching) group to implement the newly developed softcore function into the GROMACS 2022 release. In addition to the new functionality, we provided tests for the free energy kernels in GROMACS. In the future we have interest to further contribute to enhancing GROMACS' free energy calculation functionality.

7 Roadmaps

¹⁴ Y. Khalak, G. Tresdern, M. Aldeghi, H. M. Baumann, D. L. Mobley, B. de Groot, V. Gapsys (2021): Chemical Science, DOI: 10.1039/D1SC03472C

Features	2019				2020				2021				2022			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
	Improve free-energy performance	✓	✓	✓	✓					✓	✓					
Enable Accelerator/GPU-only simulations	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓										
Driving simulations from external inputs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓								
Implement long-term stable C++ and Python library APIs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓						
Constant-pH simulations					✓	✓	✓	✓								
Simple doubling of performance through multiple time stepping			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓								
Expansion and modernization of trajectory-analysis tool			✓	✓	✓	✓										
Support for tabulated interactions for both CPU and GPU					✓	✓			✓	✓						
Automated tuning for hardware					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓						
Support for Markov state model ensemble parallelism							✓	✓			✓	✓				
Deployment and acceleration for new EuroHPC architectures							✓	✓	✓	✓						
Streamlining of simulation preparation tools																
Expand support for restraint functionality											✓	✓				
Simplified free-energy calculations											✓	✓				
Molecular dynamics for large systems											✓	✓				
Evolution of Exascale-suitable task parallelism											✓	✓				
Versatile input formats for interoperability											✓	✓				

Figure 5 Development roadmap for GROMACS

Figure 6: Development roadmap for HADDOCK

WP1 WP3	Features	2019				2020				2021				2022			
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4												
Core code and usability	Python3	✓	✓	✓	✓												
	Conda					✓	✓	✓	✓								
	Further modularization					✓	✓	✓	✓								
Mutation libraries	New libraries (continued support)					✓	✓	✓	✓								
	Automated tests for mutation libraries																
	Unified amino acid and DNA mutation libraries																
Features	Amino acid protonation	✓															
	Post-translational modifications																
	Covalent modifications																
	Absolute binding free energy calculations																
Workflows						✓	✓	✓	✓								
Free energy calculations	Soft-core function implementation in Gromacs (new)					✓	✓	✓	✓								
	Free energy kernel testing in Gromacs (new)					✓	✓	✓	✓								
Covid19 related development	Workflows for protein-protein interaction scans (new)					✓	✓	✓	✓								

Bioexcel 2 extended end date

Figure 7 Development roadmap for PMX

Figure 8 Development roadmap for GROMACS-CP2K interface